

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-3, JUNE 2025

Editor-In-Chief: **Dr. Vishwanath Bite**
Managing Editor: **Dr. Madhuri Bite**

www.the-criterion.com

AboutUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/about/>

Archive: <http://www.the-criterion.com/archive/>

ContactUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/contact/>

EditorialBoard: <http://www.the-criterion.com/editorial-board/>

Submission: <http://www.the-criterion.com/submission/>

FAQ: <http://www.the-criterion.com/fa/>

ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Echoes of the Ex-centric: Reconstructing History in Toni Morrison's *Beloved*

Kiranbala Mishra

Lect. in English,
Ghess College, Ghess,
PhD Scholar (Ravenshaw University, Cuttack).

Dr. Gurudev Meher

Associate Professor,
Department of English,
Ravenshaw University Cuttack, Odisha.

Article History: Submitted-31/05/2025, Revised-18/06/2025, Accepted-22/06/2025, Published-30/06/2025.

Abstract:

History has long been considered as an objective record of past reality. But the emergence of postmodernism questions everything, including history, through its skeptical lens. Postmodernism believes that the world is perceived in terms of linguistic signs. History, too, is an interpreted version of the past, which means its understanding and perception are always linguistically conditioned. Historiographic metafiction focuses on the constructive process of historical representation. Toni Morrison's well-acclaimed novel *Beloved* delves into the atrocity of the institution of slavery. Morrison brings back the buried history of slavery by narrativizing from the perspectives of the fictionalized ex-slaves. *Beloved* portrays the inhuman experiences of the slave community by actualizing their journey of suffering into the narrative. *Beloved* advocates for these marginalized slaves, whose echoes of the painful experiences resonate throughout the novel. The incorporation of both historical and fictional elements in these novel calls for a historiographic metafictional study. In *Beloved*, memories play a dual role of serving as a medium to recover the past and to articulate the unheard voices of the slaves. These memories, from personal to collective, act as micro-narratives that undermine the

grand narrative of history from its objective proclamation. Thus, by analyzing this novel within the framework of historiographic metafiction, this paper seeks to shed light on the ex-centric characters from the overshadowed pages of the past, who strive to retain their voices in the present through the novel. Additionally, this paper aims to examine the intricate relationship between remembering and forgetting in reconstructing the historical past.

Keywords: Ex-centric, Historiographic metafiction, Parody, Memory, Grand narrative.

Introduction

African American literature studies the black people's experiences pertaining to their socio-cultural and psychological aspects. It showcases the major concerns like black identity and double consciousness, colourism, gender stereotypes, slavery and resistance. Writers like Harriet Beecher Stowe, Alice Walker, Zora Neale Hurston, Octavia Butler, etc. have made significant strides in rendering the true portrayal of black community life. Toni Morrison, an African-American writer and one of these instrumental writers, has designed a literary podium through which readers can peep into the darker history of the black community and their traumatized memories. Morrison's speciality lies in her realistic characterization and her skillful handling of the themes that bear widespread appeal, including both the personal and the universal. She "fiercely explores and exposes the African-American story in its totality and gives a universal and unique quality to her work for taking it beyond time and place" (Bommaraju 48).

Morrison, after addressing a number of socio-cultural issues experienced by the black folks in her prior novels, moves to address another poignant aspect of black history in her fifth novel, *Beloved*. By choosing slavery as its historical context and recounting the post-civil war scenario, Morrison frequently shifts the narrative between past and present in order to expose

the brutality of slavery, which has inflicted both physical and psychological wounds on black Americans.

Beloved serves as a re-evaluation and a retelling of the enslaved black people. She has given a vocal expression to the slave victims' plight and their personal suffering. This is a tale of the physical and psychological agony of the oppressed slaves, told by the oppressed ex-slaves. Through this novel, Morrison condemns the unlawful institution of slavery by unmasking its viciousness that has robbed many lives, brutalized many, and shattered familial and cultural ties.

Beloved points out the necessity of re-examining and rewriting the past from the present point of view in order to question the established norms of historical representation. The utilization of both historical and fictional elements in this novel and Morrison's reimagination of slave victims' lives situate this novel within the tradition of postmodernism. The cultural, artistic and philosophical movement of postmodernism rejects the very nature of modernism and enlightenment ideals. It rejects the enlightenment faith in rationalism, the idea of progress and the concept of universal truths. Postmodernism rather embraces subjectivity over objectivity, multiplicity over singularity and celebrates the fragmented and fluid nature of reality in opposition to the coherent and singular perception of modernism. It questions the fixity of meaning and the concept of absolute truth. Jean-François Lyotard, talking about the skeptical outlook of postmodernism towards any overarching theories, defines it as "an incredulity towards metanarratives" (xxiv). Its incredulity not only encompasses culture, art, politics and language, but also history. History, which has long been considered an objective record of the past reality, is questioned by postmodernism for its objective proclamation.

Linda Hutcheon's theory of historiographic metafiction as a postmodern subgenre deals with the discourses of fiction and history. By incorporating both the elements of history and

fiction, it sheds light on the constructive nature of historical representation. As postmodernism perceives the world in terms of linguistic signs, it shows how history can only be perceived textually. This means that our understanding of and access to the past are linguistically conditioned. Historiographic metafiction blurs the line between history and fiction in order to highlight how history, like fiction, is a linguistic construction. Another significant characteristic of historiographic metafiction is that it highlights those overlooked, the marginalized aspects of history, which Linda Hutcheon termed the 'ex-centric'. She defines, "the 'ex-centric' (be it in class, race, gender, sexual orientation, or ethnicity) take on new significance in the light of the implied recognition that our culture is not the homogeneous monolith (that is middleclass, male, heterosexual, white, western) we might have assumed" (12). Historiographic metafiction uses parody as an essential element not as a mode of mere imitation, instead to focus on the reworking and rethinking of history. It is "a critical revisiting, an ironic dialogue with the past" (5) that uses and confronts what it parodies.

Beloved contains several features of historiographic metafiction as it deals with the actual historical scenario of slavery, its aftermath in America, and the fictional representation of it. *Beloved* serves as a chronicle of the enslaved black people, which powerfully evokes their racial, gender struggles and the inhuman treatment they received at the hands of the European Americans. Narrated from multiple perspectives of the former slaves, *Beloved* eschews the traditional narrative technique and the singular portrayal of history. The journey of Sethe, her children and other slaves through the gut-wrenching torments of enslavement exposes the atrocity of slave-master relationships. Being the representatives of those marginalized slaves, these characters serve as the ex-centric, or the "off-center: ineluctably identified with the center it desires but is denied" (Hutcheon 61). Toni Morrison brings back the past of the repressed Afro-Americans into the present to resituate a place and recognition in the pages of history. Morrison challenges the grand narratives of dominant history by inscribing micronarratives of

black people's experiences and focuses on the constructive forces of history. Morrison switches her narrative between past and present frequently in this novel, and this nonlinear style foregrounds the fragmented nature of historical composition.

The former slaves of this novel, like Sethe and Paul D, are traumatized by their respective haunting pasts. Their memories of the torments, fell heavily even after their emancipation. Sethe, the sinned mother, killed her infant daughter with her own hands to protect her from forced subjugation. *Beloved* shows that although the slave victims are free beings and no longer bound by slavery, their memories of the horrific past become an inescapable trauma for them.

Toni Morrison inserts many factual details and references to slavery in this novel. Sethe's character is an intertextual allusion to the real-life slave fugitive, Margaret Garner, who escaped from a Kentucky plantation and killed one of her children in order to protect them from turning into slaves. Sethe's murder of her baby girl underscores the predicament of women slaves to whom death becomes the last option on the way to liberation. This is the only thing she could do for her children to rescue them from the horrific brutalization. This is indeed a clear portrayal of the slave victims' painful situation. Another historical account related to slavery is, the frequent and symbolic references to the Middle Passage. It is a forced voyage that used to decide the fate of the silent sufferers. Africans were forcefully transported to America as slaves with their hands and feet chained throughout this voyage across the Atlantic Ocean, causing separation from their families and homeland. During this voyage, many slaves used to die out of "epidemics, attack by pirates or enemy ships and bad weather... had also to cope with physical, sexual, and psychological abuse at the hands of their captors" (Britannica). Morrison indirectly sheds light on these traumatic experiences of the slaves through the characters. The horror of this traumatic voyage is symbolically depicted through Sethe's faint reminiscence of her mother. When she was an infant, hard to understand the cruelties of slavery,

she found her mother hanged. The only memory she has of her mother is, the branded sign on her mother's bosom that her mother has shown as a mark of identification. This sign was branded on the Africans as a mark of ownership during the voyage of the Middle Passage. For another instance, *Beloved*, the ethereal representation of Sethe's dead daughter, invokes her pathetic condition through her memory streams. *Beloved* utters a series of disjointed phrases and sentences like "I am always crouching", "the man on my face is dead," "small rats do not wait for us to sleep", "if we had more to drink, we could make tears we cannot make sweat or morning water" (210). This heart-wrenching description clearly depicts, how slaves were treated during the voyage of the Middle Passage. Morrison does not simply narrate a story on slavery, but she provides a horrifying detail about what might have happened to the slaves and their living experiences and thoughts towards the series of injustices they endured.

Beloved also refers to another remarkable historical event, the 'Fugitive Slave Law' of 1850, which gave authority to the slaveowners to recapture the escaped slaves, roaming freely in a free state, and to drag them into servitude again. The Underground Railroad, became a getaway for the enslaved to free themselves from bondage, but escaping from this hell did not completely restore their liberty; instead, they had to live under extreme fear of being recaptured. In this novel, Sethe manages to escape from the slave state to Ohio with her children, and starts living a free life. However, the arrival of the Schoolteacher, the owner of Sweet Home, where Sethe used to work, devastates her life. The fear of recapture made Sethe kill her beloved daughter, and as she was about to kill the other three children, she was jailed and ostracized by her own community. By inserting the factual details, Toni Morrison attempts to restore the forgotten past, which serves as an essential aspect of African American history.

Morrison provides an authentic account of the black people that challenges the Eurocentric standpoint of history. Through this novel, she raises a historical consciousness by re-centering the ex-centric. Historiographic metafiction confronts a singular version of history

by engaging multiple histories together in order to show the variety of subjective experiences which cannot be generalized. In *Beloved*, each character projects their own personal history and demands a historical presence. The Sweet Home plantation is the representation of the social injustices of that time, as it serves like a cage for the enslaved Afro-American, where they were perceived as animals and physically tortured. Sethe as an ex-centric character, expresses her own part of suffering through memory. She witnessed all her dreams falling apart that she aspired as a daughter, wife and a mother. Morrison portrays Sethe, with utmost care so that her character reflects the thousands of slave women who dared to dream of freedom for her and her family, rather than live mired in slavery. Living the life of a slave on this plantation, she was mortally humiliated. The School teacher's nephews not only assaulted Sethe sexually, even during her pregnancy, but also snatched her milk and mercilessly inflicted physical torture on her. The scars on Sethe's back are a permanent stigma on the unjust system of slavery that reveals the intensity of the harsh punishment the slaves used to endure.

Sethe, as a possessive and protective mother, never desired her children to suffer from the same corporeal and psychological affliction that she faced as a slave, and that led her to commit infanticide. But, the memory of this horrible crime engulfed Sethe completely, so that she lived with the deep regret that she could not provide a beautiful life for Beloved. Society's crudeness made Sethe a helpless mother, which is further revealed by the way she struggled to memorialized her deceased daughter by giving her a proper burial place. For this, Sethe was compelled to sleep with the engraver to etch the name 'Beloved' on her dead daughter's tombstone. As she recalls, "Ten minutes for seven letters. With another ten, could she have gotten "Dearly" too? She had not thought to ask him, and it bothered her still that it might have been possible—that for twenty minutes, a half hour, say, she could have had the whole thing..." (5). These powerful words of Sethe reveal the immorality and mistreatment of society towards black women.

Paul D, another ex-centric character of this text, who demands a historical recognition as a slave victim. Paul D expresses his version of history and the vivacity of his endured torments. Slaves were usually brought and sold like property. For the slave catchers, slaves were just several heads through which profit could be made. Thus, they were not valued as humans. Paul D recalls the inhuman treatment he received in Sweet Home and Alfred, and he becomes devoid of emotional attachment. As the sole survivor from Sweet Home plantation, Paul D lost all his friends to the brutality of slavery. He is so burdened with past trauma that he experiences self-alienation, and he has closed off his heart to others. After years of aimless wandering, Paul D finds solace in Sather's company. While reflecting on his horrifying experiences of humiliation in Georgia, where he was imprisoned in an underground cell for trying to kill his new owner, he expresses to Sethe how he was feeling insignificant and inferior to a rooster, "Mister was allowed to be and stay what he was. But I wasn't allowed to be and stay what I was. Even if you cooked him, you'd be cooking a rooster named Mister. But there was no way I would ever be Paul D again, living or dead. Schoolteacher changed me. I was something else, and that something was less than a chicken sitting in the sun on a tub" (72).

Beloved serves as a multilayered storyline unfolding various aspects of slave life like their unfulfilled love, resistance against atrocities and collective suffering. The other slaves of Sweet Home plantation, such as Halle, Sixo, Paul A, Paul F, were too victimized mortally and mentally; some of them were killed and found mutilated as they tried to escape from this bondage. Paul D laments over losing his friends, "One crazy, one sold, one missing, one burnt" (72). Sixo's dream of living a free and happy life with his lover ended on an unhappy note. He was caught and burned alive before he could see his unborn child. Halle, Sethe's husband, was driven mad and lost. Through all these individual stories, Morrison exposes how multiple families were ruined because of slavery.

Historiographic metafiction perceives historical writing as a subjective process. As a historiographic metafiction, *Beloved* examines the role of forgetting and recalling in interpreting the historical past. Memory becomes a key element for playing the dual role of serving as an instrument in recovering the buried history of slave victims and voicing their individual and collective suffering. Memory in this novel acts as a threatening agent, the real ghost to the slave victims, that haunts them and victimizes them in the present. For the ex-slaves, memorizing their past is like nourishing their physical and psychological wounds. Thus, the characters try to escape from the past trauma by forgetting it consciously. For instance, Baby Suggs hardly remembers all her children. Sethe suggests, “That’s all you let yourself remember” (5). This sheds light on the unreliability of memory and testimonies in shaping historical records and their inherent subjectivity. Sethe struggles to control her memories that continually interfere with her present life. This aggravates after the sudden appearance of her dead daughter, Beloved, who serves as a symbol of her horrifying past, and the physical representation of Sethe’s past guilt. At the novel’s end, the community’s exorcism of Beloved from the house is a metaphor for their collective desire to get rid of their past. This forgetting and recalling of past memories reveals that history cannot be exactly portrayed. This scene of forgetting acts as a parody of traditional historiography that deliberately omits certain historical aspects.

Historiographic metafiction “plays upon the truth and lies of the historical record...in order to foreground the possible mnemonic failures of recorded history” (Hutcheon 114). Historiographic metafiction deliberately alters certain historical aspects in order to challenge the objective claim of recorded history. Morrison, though, has adapted the real historical event as the novel’s backdrop, still manipulates certain aspects. For instance, Sethe’s killing of her child is modelled on Margarete Garner, who was in reality imprisoned not because of the crime of infanticide, but rather for escaping. But Sethe, in this novel, is charged with infanticide. By

using the real historical context, Morrison parodies the traditional process of historical writing and manipulates its aspects. She highlights that historical interpretation can never be objective, as it can involve personal biases and deliberate manipulation by historians.

The micronarratives of slave victims 'experiences challenge the grand narrative of the Eurocentric perspective. According to Craig Seligman, *Beloved*, "instead of showing how slavery dehumanized both slave and master, it treats dehumanization as a white myth: the slaves have had painfully full spiritual lives (enriched, if anything, by suffering), where the masters are spiritually withered" (7). This Euro-centric misperception of the dehumanization of slaves is a grand narrative that this novel undermines by projecting the spiritual, emotional and communal strength of these slave victims, who have no doubt exhibited their human strength by profound resilience. Their familial love, the pangs of separation and the community support glorify the black existence.

Conclusion

Toni Morrison's *Beloved*, as a historiographic metafiction, critically examines the nature of historical representation. By reinvestigating the historical past, Morrison not only emphasizes the necessity of reinterpreting history but also contends that, the traditional approach is an objective and generalized discourse. The free articulation of the voices of the ex-centric characters in this narrative undermines the grand narrative of Euro-centric views on slavery. Morrison's use of memory as an essential tool underscores the impact of forgetting and recalling in shaping historical records and perceives history as a subjective construction of the past.

Works Cited:

- Bommaraju, Anuradha Surya Kumari. *Mothers and Daughters in the Novels of Toni Morrison: A Select Study*. 2015. Andhra U, PhD dissertation. *Sodhganga*, hdl.handle.net/10603/360386. Accessed 15 Feb. 2025.
- Hutcheon, Linda. *A Poetics of Postmodernism: History, Theory, Fiction*. Routledge, 1988.
- Lyotard, Jean-François. *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge*. 1979. Translated by Geoff Bennington and Brian Massumi, U of Minnesota P, 1984.
- Morrison, Toni. *Beloved*. E-book ed., Vintage International, 2004.
- Seligman, Craig. "Toni Morrison." *The Threepenny Review*, no. 52, Threepenny Review, 1993, pp. 7–9, *JSTOR*. www.jstor.org/stable/4384155. Accessed 21 Feb. 2025.
- The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica. "Middle Passage." *Encyclopædia Britannica*, 15 Feb. 2025, www.britannica.com/topic/Middle-Passage-slave-trade. Accessed 20 Feb. 2025.